

LIFESKILLS AND IT'S IMPACT ON HUMAN HEALTH**Dr. Sou. Shobha Arun Paudmal***Assist. Professor (Dept. of Commerce and Management)**Night College of Arts and Commerce, Ichalkaranji***ABSTRACT**

Psychosocial competence is a person's ability to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. It is a person's ability to maintain a state of mental well-being and to demonstrate this in adaptive and positive behaviour while interacting with others, his/her culture and environment. Psychosocial competence has an important role to play in the promotion of health in its broadest sense; in terms of physical, mental and social well-being. In particular, where health problems are related to behaviour, and where the behaviour is related to an inability to deal effectively with stresses and pressures in life, the enhancement of psychosocial competence could make an important contribution. This is especially important for health promotion at a time when behaviour is more and more implicated as the source of health problems. The most direct interventions for the promotion of psychosocial competence are those which enhance the person's coping resources, and personal and social competencies. In school-based programmes for children and adolescents, this can be done by the teaching of Lifeskills in a supportive learning environment.

Key Words: *Psychosocial, Behaviour, Interventions, Adolescents, Environment etc.*

1. INRODUCTION

The Lifeskills programme is a school based programme where Lifeskills are imparted in a supportive learning environment. They are applicable for all ages of children and adolescents in school. However, the age group targeted is mainly 10-18, adolescent years, since young people of this age group seem to be most vulnerable to behaviour related health problems. The programme is for the promotion of health and well being and targeted group is all children. Life skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. Described in this way, skills that can be said to be life skills are innumerable, and the nature and definition of lifeskills are likely to differ across cultures and settings. However, analysis of the lifeskills field suggests that there is a core set of skills that are at the heart of skills-based initiatives for the promotion of the health and well-being of children and adolescents.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the concept of Lifeskills.
2. To study the different key Lifeskills.
3. To study the impact of Lifeskills on Human Health.

3. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The present study has been descriptive; the data for this study were obtained from secondary sources. The secondary data has been collected from various references which already existed in published form; part of the paper is based on literature review the method comprising of collecting all the available papers relating to the theme and selecting relevant papers/books for the review purpose. Selection of the paper is done on the basis of their relevance and contribution to the body of knowledge. The author has made an attempt to do primary reading of the selected papers which will constitute the core of this review study.

4. CONCEPT OF LIFESKILLS

Lifeskills have been defined as “the abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life” (WHO). ‘Adaptive’ means that a person is flexible in approach and is able to adjust in different circumstances. ‘Positive behaviour’ implies that a person is forward looking and even in difficult situations, can find a ray of hope and opportunities to find solutions.

5. KEY LIFESKILLS

Lifeskills include psychosocial competencies and interpersonal skills that help people make informed decisions, solve problems, think critically and creatively, communicate effectively, build healthy relationships, empathize with others, and cope with managing their lives in a healthy and productive manner. The Ten core Lifeskills as laid down by WHO are:

1. Self-awareness
2. Empathy
3. Critical thinking
4. Creative thinking
5. Decision making
6. Problem Solving
7. Effective communication
8. Interpersonal relationship
9. Coping with stress
10. Coping with emotion

6. IMPACT OF LIFESKILLS ON HUMAN HEALTH

- ❖ Lifeskills are essentially those abilities that help promote overall wellbeing and competence in students as they face the realities of life.
- ❖ Lifeskills are the beginning of wisdom which focuses on behaviour change or developmental approach designed to address a balance of three areas- knowledge, attitude and skills.
- ❖ Lifeskills enable individuals to translate knowledge, attitude and values into actual abilities-i.e. what to do and how to do it, given the scope and opportunity to do so.
- ❖ Lifeskills however are not a panacea of “how to do abilities” as they are not the only factors that affect behaviour. There are many factors such as social support, culture and environment that affect motivation and ability to behave in positive ways.
- ❖ Effective acquisition and application of Lifeskills can influence the way one feels about others, ourselves and will equally influence the way we are perceived by others. It contributes to perception of self confidence and self esteem.
- ❖ Lifeskills for psychosocial competence needs to be distinguished from other important skills that young people will acquire as they grow up such as reading, numbers, technical and livelihood skills.
- ❖ Lifeskills education involves a dynamic teaching process. The methods used to facilitate this active involvement includes working in small groups and pairs, brainstorming, role plays, games and debates.
- ❖ Many Lifeskills are required to manage a particular situation effectively. In a way, various Lifeskills work best in conjunction. In fact, the appropriate combination of Lifeskills in a given moment is an art.
- ❖ Children learn their Lifeskills from parents, teachers and significant others who act as their role model. They gradually learn to use a particular skill effectively in diverse situation to cope with challenges of life.

7. CONCLUSION

In a constantly changing environment, having Lifeskills is an essential part of being able to meet the challenges of everyday life. The dramatic changes in global economies over the past five years have been matched with the transformation in technology and these are all impacting on education, the workplace and our home life. To cope with the increasing pace and change of modern life, students need new Lifeskills such as the ability to deal with stress and frustration. Today's students will have many new jobs over the course of their lives, with associated pressures and the need for flexibility.

8. REFERENCES

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